

Basic meteorological observations in the Centrumlø region of northeast Greenland

Anika DONNER¹, Paul TÖCHTERLE¹, Gina E MOSELEY¹

¹Institute of Geology, University of Innsbruck, Innrain 52, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria
E-mail: Anika Donner (anika.donner@uibk.ac.at)

Abstract: In recent years, northeast Greenland has increasingly become a centre for palaeoclimate research; however, placing palaeoclimate observations in the context of present climatology has been hampered by the limited number of meteorological stations that exist in this remote region. During the 2015 and 2019 Greenland Caves Project expeditions in the Centrumlø/Grottedal region (Lat: +80°), basic spot measurements were taken to obtain observational knowledge about the meteorology of the area. The results show an air temperature range between 6.1°C and 18.9°C and low wind speeds up to 4m s⁻¹. These observations are generally in agreement with previous studies, suggesting a more continental climate in the ice-free Centrumlø/Grottedal region as compared to measurements from meteorological stations on the Greenland ice sheet (part of the PROMICE project) and on the coast (Station Nord, Danmarkshavn). Reliable meteorological measurements operating over longer timescales would be helpful for palaeoclimate studies being conducted in the Centrumlø/Grottedal region.

Received: 24 May 2020; Accepted: 19 June 2020.

Introduction

Northeast Greenland has been a location for geological research and exploration since the mid-1950s (Higgins, 2010; Moseley, 2020; Smith and Rasmussen, 2020). In recent years, however, there has been a growing interest in palaeoclimate research, e.g., Greenland Caves Project (GCP) (Moseley *et al.*, 2020), EGRIP ice core (EGRIP, 2020), northeast Greenland Ice Stream (NEGIS) (NEGIS, 2020). This is partly a consequence of the need to understand more about past climate and environmental changes in this highly sensitive region where temperature and precipitation are projected to increase in future decades (Bintanja and Selten, 2014; GISTEMP Team, 2016; Koenigk *et al.*, 2013; Melles *et al.*, 2012; Meredith *et al.*, 2019). To place the palaeoclimate observations in the context of the present climatology, modern meteorological observations are required (Schuster *et al.*, in prep.). Unfortunately, in this remote and

uninhabited region, few permanent meteorological stations exist. The longest-running station in the wider area (1949 to Present) is found on the coast at Danmarkshavn (Lat: +76.7694°, Long: -18.6681°) (DMI, 2012; ISAAFFIK, 2018a), nearly 400km to the south of the Centrumlø/Grottedal region where the GCP has been operating. For Station Nord (Lat: +81.6033°, Long: -16.6633°), which is also located on the coast and situated 180km to the north of Centrumlø/Grottedal, meteorological observations since 1961 are available (ISAAFFIK, 2018b; DMI, 2020a). Additionally, two meteorological stations (KPC_L, Lat: +79.91667°, Long: -24.08333°, 370m above sea level; KPC_U, Lat: 79.83333°, Long: -25.16667°, 870m above sea level) that belong to the Programme for Monitoring of the Greenland Ice Sheet project (PROMICE) (Fausto and van As, 2019) are located just 40km and 60km respectively to the southwest of Centrumlø/Grottedal, but these are situated on the ice sheet and have been operational only since July 2008 (van As *et al.*, 2011). None of these weather stations are thus ideally placed to provide meteorological observations representative of the ice-free continental climate at the GCP field sites.

During the 2015 and 2019 expeditions, various basic meteorological measurements were taken in order to obtain some observational knowledge about the meteorology of the Centrumlø/Grottedal area. The results are presented here and placed in the context of existing knowledge.

Methods

Observations of ambient air temperature, relative humidity, dew point, wind speed and wind direction were made in the vicinity of Centrumlø/Grottedal, using a calibrated handheld Kestrel 4500 weather meter in 2015 (Fig. 1) and a calibrated handheld Kestrel 5500 weather meter in 2019. When taking measurements, the device was held at approximately 1m above ground level and pointed upwind. The accuracy or precision of each measured variable for both weather meters, if not indicated otherwise, are as follows (Kestrel, n.d., 2015):

Figure 1: Gina Moseley taking spot weather measurements in 2015. [Photo: Robbie Shone.]

air temperature: $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$; resolution (res): 0.1°C ; relative humidity: $\pm 3\%$ (4500) and $\pm 2\%$ (5500), res: 0.1% ; dew point: $\pm 1.9^{\circ}\text{C}$, res: 0.1°C ; pressure: $\pm 1.0\text{hPa}$ (4500) and $\pm 1.5\text{hPa}$ at 25°C (5500), res: 0.1hPa ; and wind speed: $>3\%$ of readings, res: 0.1m/s . The authors appreciate that this method of data collection has many limitations, and that this prevents substantial interpretation or conclusions being made. Nevertheless, the opportunity is taken here to provide the results, because they might be useful for other studies.

Results

Measurements taken during the 2015 and 2019 expeditions are listed in Table 1. In total, 18 sets of measurements were taken on 17 days. For 2015, 13 measurements were taken over 12 days in August, whereas for 2019, 5 measurements were taken over 7 days in July. Measurements were made within a radius of 18km in locations representing comparable climates and environments. In 2015 measurements were taken only between 07:55 and 18:35, with most measurements taken before noon and one measurement with unknown time. In 2019, measurements were taken between 10:00 and 20:45; two of these were taken before noon, one in the early afternoon and two in the evening. Despite the whole region experiencing 24-hour sunlight during the 2015 and 2019 expeditions, to some extent the measurements are biased towards conditions during the “day”, because it did become cooler at “night”, once the sun dropped below the horizon.

The highest recorded air temperature in the Centrumso/Grottedal region was 18.9°C at 14:44 on 13 August 2015, followed by 18.0°C at 11:00 on 09 July 2019. The lowest recorded air temperature in the study area was 6.1°C at 10:01 on 07 August 2015. Wind speeds were never greater than 4.0ms^{-1} , with the general direction being from the southeast to southsouthwest and west in 2015, and northnorthwest in 2019 (Table 1).

Discussion

Whilst acknowledging the limitations of the data-collection methods as well as the lack of results preventing a full statistical analysis, the recorded air temperatures of the Centrumso/Grottedal area can be considered in relation to existing observations for the wider area. In July 1960, mean daily air temperatures at Centrumso ranged from $12\text{--}14^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Krinsley, 1960), with a recorded maximum and minimum air temperature of 16°C and 2°C respectively (Needleman, 1960). The 1960 expedition was not present in the region during August. In comparison, measurements in this study recorded a range of 10.1 to 18.0°C in July 2019 (and 6.1 to 18.9°C in August 2015), though these are spot measurements and might not represent daily maxima and minima. In fact, since this study did not record measurements at ‘night’, it is almost certain that the daily absolute minimum air temperatures were not recorded. The maximum recorded air temperatures in this study are, however, found to be comparable between August 2015 and July 2019, and with July 1960 (Needleman, 1960).

Date	Latitude / Longitude	Time	Air Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Relative Humidity (%)	Dew Point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Wind speed (ms^{-1})	Wind direction	Maximum Daily Air Temperature at SN ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Maximum Daily Air Temperature at DN ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
29.07.2015	80.15 -22.51	—	10.4	63.5	3.1	4.0	SSE	0.6	9.5
30.07.2015	80.21 -21.57	13:50	13.0	63.0	6.1	0.4	SW	8.9	7.7
01.08.2015	80.34 -21.50	09:30	16.3	46.3	4.6	2.1	SE	9.9	13.1
02.08.2015	80.34 -21.50	09:19	14.4	46.2	2.9	2.6	SE	9.4	11.7
04.08.2015	80.38 -21.71	07:55	12.2	53.9	2.4	0.0	None	11.6	8.4
06.08.2015	80.38 -21.71	11:00	7.5	63.0	1.1	3.3	SSW	11.8	13.1
07.08.2015	80.34 -21.50	10:01	6.1	75.6	3.6	2.1	SSW	6.8	6.5
10.08.2015	80.21 -21.57	11:37	7.4	84.6	4.6	1.8	W	4.9	6.5
10.08.2015	80.17 -22.24	16:07	17.4	67.9	11.2	0.4	W	4.9	6.5
11.08.2015	80.20 -21.95	15:55	13.1	60.4	2.4	2.4	SSW	10.1	6.7
12.08.2015	80.15 -22.51	18:35	13.7	58.0	3.8	2.0	SW	11.5	6.9
13.08.2015	80.15 -22.51	14:44	18.9	64.5	7.4	1.4	S	8.9	6.2
14.08.2015	80.15 -22.51	10:45	9.7	71.1	4.5	1.6	SE	11.1	6.4
05.07.2019	80.38 -21.74	10:00	13.0	43.0	3.0	2.5	NNW	4.0	13.6
08.07.2019	80.10 -22.52	19:00	12.5	48.0	1.9	2.6	NNW	13.0	12.1
09.07.2019	80.10 -22.52	11:00	18.0	31.0	0.4	1.5	NNW	10.6	12.7
10.07.2019	80.10 -22.52	13:40	15.5	42.0	2.6	1.7	NNW	8.0	12.0
11.07.2019	80.10 -22.52	20:45	10.1	57.0	1.8	3.0	NNW	4.4	7.3
Maximum Values		07:55	18.9	84.6	11.2	4.0		13.0	13.6
Minimum Values		20:45	6.1	31.0	0.4	0.0		0.6	6.2

Table 1: 2015 and 2019 expeditions: basic meteorological measurements in the Centrumso/Grottedal region. SN = Station Nord. DH = Danmarkshavn.

Figure 2: Chris Blakeley releases a weather balloon from Danmarkshavn in 2019. [Photo: Robbie Shone.]

Farther afield, the air temperatures recorded by the KPC_L and KPC_U meteorological stations were 3.7°C and 0.22°C respectively at 15:00 on 13 August 2015, and 4.6°C and 1.4°C respectively at 11:00 on 09 July 2019 (Fausto *et al.*, 2019) (i.e. significantly lower than the 18.9°C and 18.0°C recorded in Centrumso/Grottedal at the same time). The highest ever recorded air temperatures at the two PROMICE weather stations are 13.34°C at KPC_L on 19 July 2012, and 5.73°C at KPC_U on 16 June 2014 (Fausto *et al.*, 2019). The highest daily mean air temperatures since the stations began operation in 2008 do not exceed c.7°C at KPC_L and c.4.5°C at KPC_U (Fausto *et al.*, 2019). Even though these two stations are located just 40–60km southwest of the Centrumso/Grottedal region, the data from the stations on the ice sheet indicate a tendency towards lower summer air temperatures than in the Centrumso/Grottedal region. Reliable measurements over longer timescales are needed in the Centrumso/Grottedal region to inform and support more-robust conclusions.

At the coastal weather stations of Danmarkshavn (c.400km to the southeast; Fig.2) and Station Nord (c.160km to the northeast), the recorded maximum air temperatures on 13 August 2015, were 6.2°C and 8.9°C respectively, and 12.7°C and 10.6°C respectively on 09 July 2019 (DMI, 2020b). Spot air temperature measurements as recorded in this study were thus considerably higher than the maximum recorded daily air temperature at the two coastal meteorological stations. Specifically, the majority (14 out of 18) of the Grottedal/Centrumso air temperature measurements from this study exceed the maximum daily air temperatures at Station Nord for the respective days, whereas 16 do so at Danmarkshavn (Table 1) (DMI, 2020b). The highest air temperature recorded at Station Nord between 2014 and May 2020 was 16.6°C in July 2017, whereas at the more southerly Danmarkshavn it was 19.7°C in August 2019 (DMI, 2020b). The data for the most recent complete standard reference period (1981–2010) show that the mean maximum daily air temperature in July at Danmarkshavn was 7.2°C. Such information is not available for Station Nord, where the mean July air temperature over the only available reference period (1961–1990) was 3.4°C (DMI, 2020a). Thus, similar to the PROMICE weather stations (Fausto *et al.*, 2019), the Danmarkshavn and Station Nord coastal meteorological stations also appear to indicate a cooler summer climate than that currently experienced in the Grottedal/Centrumso region.

Conclusion

In this report, the results of basic meteorological observations of the Centrumso/Grottedal area are presented for August 2015 and July 2019. Comparing the rudimentary air temperature measurements to those of the closest weather stations on the

nearby ice sheet, as well as to those of the two weather stations on the coast, suggests that the climate of the Centrumso/Grottedal region is more continental, with warmer summers, as compared to the ice sheet and coastal regions. Reliable observations and measurements of the current climatology over longer timescales in the Centrumso/Grottedal region are needed, so that results of palaeoclimate observations can be considered in the context of the current climatology.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the Austrian Science Fund (project no. Y 1162-N37 to Gina Moseley). The Greenland government are thanked for permission to undertake this fieldwork (KNNO Expedition Permit C-19-32; Scientific Survey Licence VU-00150; Greenland National Museum and Archives 2019/01).

Additionally, we thank the logistics companies Polog, Air Greenland, and Norlandair for field support. Data from the Programme for Monitoring of the Greenland Ice Sheet (PROMICE) were provided by the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) [promice.dk]. Lindsey Nicholson is thanked for providing helpful feedback.

References

- Bintanja, R and Selten, F M, 2014. Future increases in Arctic precipitation linked to local evaporation and sea-ice retreat. *Nature*, Vol.509, 479–482.
- DMI, 2012. Technical Report 12-04. Greenland – DMI Historical Climate Data Collection 1873-2011: With Danish Abstracts.
- DMI, 2020a. Klimanormaler for Grønland: dmi.dk/vejarkiv/normaler-gronland [Accessed 06 May 2020.]
- DMI, 2020b. Vejarkiv: dmi.dk/vejarkiv [Accessed 06 May 2020.]
- EGRIP, 2020. About EastGRIP: eastgrip.org/About.html [Accessed 01 May 2020.]
- Fausto, R S and van As, D, 2019. Programme for monitoring of the Greenland ice sheet (PROMICE): Automatic weather station data. Version: v03, Dataset published via Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland. Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS), 2020. Programme for Monitoring of the Greenland Ice Sheet: promice.dk/WeatherStations.html [Accessed May 2020.]
- GISTEMP Team, 2016. *GISS Surface temperature analysis (GISTEMP)*. 989–990 in Shepherd, T G (Ed.). Effects of a warming Arctic. *Science*, Vol.347.
- Higgins, A K, 2010. Exploration history and place names of northern East Greenland. *Geological Survey of Denmark Bulletin*, Vol.21, 368pp.
- ISAAFFIK, 2018a. Danmarkshavn - DMI weather and radio sounding station, isaaffik.org/danmarkshavn-dmi-weather-and-radio-sounding-station [Accessed 01 May 2020.]
- ISAAFFIK, 2018b. Station Nord - DMI weather station: isaaffik.org/station-nord-dmi-weather-station [Accessed 01 May 2020.]
- Kestrel, n.d. Product Specifications for Kestrel 4 Series Weather/Environmental Meters: cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0084/9012/files/Kestrel_CoC.pdf [Accessed 07 May 2020.]
- Kestrel, 2015. Product Specifications for Kestrel 5 Series Weather/Environmental Meters: cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0084/9012/files/329002_0_15.10.16.pdf [Accessed 30 April 2020.]
- Koenigk, T, Brodeau, L, Graversen, R G, Karlsson, J, Svensson, G, Tjernström, M, Willén, U and Wyser, K, 2013. Arctic climate change in 21st century CMIP5 simulations with EC-Earth. *Climate Dynamics*, Vol.40, 2719–2743.
- Krinsley, D B, 1960. Limnological investigations at Centrum Sø, Northeast Greenland. *Polarforschung*, Vol.30, 24–32.
- Melles, M, Brigham-Grette, J, Minyuk, P S, Nowaczyk, N R, Wennrich, V, DeConto, R M, Anderson, P M, Andreev, A A, Coletti, A, Cook, T L, Haltia-Hovi, E, Kukkonen, M, Lozhkin, A V, Rosén, P, Tarasov, P, Vogel, H and Wagner, B, 2012. 2.8 million years of Arctic climate change from Lake El'gygytgyn, NE Russia. *Science*, Vol.337, 315–320.
- Meredith, M, Sommerkorn, M, Cassotta, S, Derksen, C, Ekaykin, A, Hollowed, A, Kofinas, G, Mackintosh, A, Melbourne-Thomas, J, Muelbert, M M C, Ottersen, G, Pritchard, H and Schuur, E A G, 2019. *Polar Regions*. 203–320 in IPCC - Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate.
- Moseley, G E, 2020. History of exploration in northeast Greenland. *Cave and Karst Science*, Vol.47(2), 55–59
- Moseley, G E, Barton, H A, Spötl, C, Töchterle, P, Smith, M P, Bjerkenäs, S E, Blakeley, C, Hodkinson, P D, Shone, R C, Sivertsen, H C and Wright, M, 2020. Cave discoveries and speleogenetic features in northeast Greenland. *Cave and Karst Science*, Vol.47, No.2, 74–87.
- Needleman, S M, 1960. Soil Science Studies at Centrum Sø, Northeast Greenland, 1960. *Polarforschung*, Vol.30, 33–41.
- NEGIS, 2020. Greenland in a Warmer Climate: community.dur.ac.uk/negis [Accessed 01 May 2020.]
- Schuster, L, Maussion, F, Langhamer, L and Moseley, G E, [In Prep.] Lagrangian detection of moisture sources for an arid region in Northeast Greenland: relations to the North-Atlantic Oscillation and temporal trends from 1979 to 2017. *In preparation for Weather and Climate Dynamics*
- Smith, M P and Rasmussen, J A, 2020. The geology of the Centrumso area of Kronprins Christian Land, northeast Greenland, and lithological constraints on speleogenesis. *Cave and Karst Science*, Vol.47(2), 60–65.
- van As, D, Fausto, R S, Ahlström, A P, Andersen, S B, Andersen, M L, Citterio, M, Edelvang, K, Graversen, P, Machguth, H, Nick, F M, Faezeh, M, Nielsen, S and Weidick, A, 2011. Programme for Monitoring of the Greenland Ice Sheet (PROMICE): first temperature and ablation records. *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin*, Vol.23, 73–76.